

The Role of Quality Assurance in Improving Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) In Architecture Kaduna Polytechnic, Nigeria

Fatima Baba Ciroma¹

Aisha Wali Aminu-Umar²

Ndandok, Christy Thyeno³

*Architecture Department College of Environmental Studies Kaduna Polytechnic, Barnawa Kaduna
state (Nigeria).*

aminanazif@yahoo.co.uk

ciromafb@gmail.com

ayshaaminuumar@gmail.com

Abstract

Quality Assurance (QA) and Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) in Architecture are two widely discussed concepts in specialised skill-focused education. The ineffective or absence of QA has been identified by policymakers as an inhibition to the realization of the goals of TVET. Therefore, this paper aims to examine the impact of QA on TVET in Nigeria. This study becomes imperative to provide a reliable assessment and research-based evidence on TVET in Nigeria. The quantitative research method relies on the survey strategy for data collection. The key sample locations will be Kaduna Polytechnic, Kaduna, Federal College of Education Zaria, Nuhu Bamalli Polytechnic, Zaria and Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, from which a sample size of 150 staff and student respondents will be selected using a purposive sampling technique. The returned questionnaires would be analysed electronically, and the findings would be systematically presented using descriptive and inferential statistics. The major finding from the survey would be that the impact of TVET has not been impressive because of ineffective QA at all levels. Further, the findings recommend that The general public, especially policymakers, must be properly educated and sensitized about the true purpose of TVET as it relates to the fields of architecture and environmental science if TVET is to promote employability and national development. When correctly implemented, this strategy would hasten the shift in attitudes and inspire support from parents, students, wards, and all other stakeholders in Kaduna State. The practical implication of the paper is that for TVET to be impactful on technical progress, employability, and national development there is a need for the policymakers to focus on critical areas such as finance, access/participation, quality

assurance, and relevance of the programme to the needs of Kaduna Polytechnic, Kaduna state, Nigeria. The study concludes that policymakers should focus on critical areas such as finance, access/participation, quality assurance, and relevance of the program to the needs of Kaduna Polytechnic for TVET to be impactful on technical progress, employability, and national development.

Keywords: Educational Objectives Kaduna Technical Vocational Education and Training, Quality Assurance,

1. INTRODUCTION

Nigeria is the most populous black nation in Africa where one out of every five Africans lives. (Adebakin, 2012) However, the poverty situation in Nigeria is alarming, especially among the youth. Though, Poverty and unemployment, especially among the youth a global phenomenon. For instance, findings released by the National Board for Technical Education (2011) show that youth (18-30) make up nearly half (47 per cent) of the world's unemployed. Accordingly, Ball's, (1994) findings show that of the world's 550 million working poor who cannot lift themselves above US \$1 per day, poverty is youth. The estimation of poverty in 2004 halving the youth globally indicates that unemployment among youth would increase if adequate measures were not put in place to tackle the menace. Badawi, (2013) opined that would lower the poverty level and add to Growth Domestic Product (GDP).

Worries about the indigenous peoples' occupational capacities, unskilled workforce, and demands of work environment coupled with concerns about educational achievement, are driving unprecedented demand for good and quality services derived from personnel who are vocationally skilful. But it is only a good academic programme that could contribute to this skills acquisition and healthy development by providing opportunities for positive learning and growth (Becker, 2009; National Board for Technical Education, 2011).

Learning is positively imparted if learners could practice what they were taught in character, implementation, and production. Hence, there was a search for a good educational system to inculcate these learning attributes in Nigerian youths. In the search, various committees, commissions, and academic boards were inaugurated by the Federal Government of Nigeria dating back from 1976 through 1985. Conclusively, the system of education which falls within the domain of technical and vocational education and training (TVET) was widely acclaimed and recommended at several fora as the provider of these

performance attributes in character, implementation, and production. This is so because TVET encourages skills acquisition, knowledge and attitudes needed for professional careers Eze and Okafor, (2012) and through its orientation, the social and economic inclusion of the rural population and the marginalized communities are addressed.

The paper aims to assess the Role of Quality Assurance in improving Technical Vocational Education and Training in Architecture at Kaduna Polytechnic, Nigeria. Based on the foregoing, this empirical paper is premised on two objectives. The first is to examine the impact of quality assurance on TVET in Nigeria with a specific emphasis on technological progress, employability, and national development (Eze and Okafor, 2012). The second intent of the paper is to carry out a quality assurance survey on selected TVET institutions in Kaduna state (Nigeria) using four quality assurance indicators (QAIs).

2. MEASURING FUNCTIONALITY OF TVET

Quality Assurance Indicators To avoid measuring TVET performance haphazardly by the rule of thumb, educationists have developed quality assurance indicators (QAIs), which give information and statistics about educational effectiveness, efficiency and performance in different contexts (Chalmers, 2008). There are several quality assurance indicators, but the common point of convergence among all the quality metrics is the need for objective evaluation and quality improvement. According to Adegbesan,(2011), the five key components of quality assurance indicators are:

- (a) What learners gain;
- (b) Quality Learning Environments.
- (c) Quality Content;
- (d) Processes that support Quality; and
- (e) Outcomes from the learning environment.

Additional quality assurance indicators include:

- (i) The learners' behavioural characteristics, attributes and demographic factors,
- (ii) The teacher's professional competencies/pedagogic skills,
- (iii) The teaching processes, curriculum and learning environment,
- (iv) The outcomes of education (Adegbesan, 2011)

Besides, quality assurance indicators could be classified as simple quality indicators, performance quality indicators and general quality indicators (Cave *et al.*, 1997; Chalmers, 2008). In practice, simple and performance quality indicators are quantitative in nature. The simple indicators are employed by quality assurance evaluators to provide a relatively unbiased description of a situation or process in the school system. The result of such QA is often expressed as absolute figures devoid of valued judgment.

Performance indicators on the other hand are QA that is tied to a particular standard of learning/teaching, educational objectives, goal of examination, evaluation of management/teacher/amenities et cetera. The outcome is relative rather than absolute and it is heavily dependent on valued judgment. The general indicators however are used for QA that is essentially externally driven to elicit opinions, survey findings or general statistics (Adebakin and Raimi, 2012; Amodu, 2011; Amuta, 2013).

2.1 Environmental Factors Affecting the Quality of TVET

Nigeria's low-quality TVET is linked to several environmental factors. The foremost environmental factor is in the effective implementation of the TVET curriculum. According to Onyesom and Ashibogwu (2013), the outcome of Monitoring Learning Achievement (MLA) in Nigeria revealed that "there is a wide gap between the intended curriculums (theory) and the achieved curriculum (practice)."

The constraint of translating educational curriculum into reality in the domains of colleges, polytechnics and universities had been a recurring implementation issue in Nigeria for a very long time; this ugly development is linked to a cluster of constraints like inadequacy of experts, irrelevant textbooks, ineffective teaching method, paucity of learning tools for practical-oriented exercises and poor funding of institutions (Filloux, 1993; Fadokun, 2005; Gabadeen and Raimi, 2012). It is therefore right to conclude that several laudable educational programmes in Nigeria were compromised mid-way through implementation because of the institution's inability to effectively translate the objectives of the curriculum into practical realities (Bowles and Gintis, 1976; Broudy, 1981; Borden and Bottrill, 1994).

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research adopts quantitative research methods. The required quantitative data were sourced from Kaduna Polytechnic, Kaduna, Federal College of Education Zaria, Nuhu Bamalli Polytechnic, Zaria and Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria and other institutions using a structured questionnaire instrument with 54 items. The homogeneous nature of TVET institutions in Kaduna state (Nigeria) made the purposive sampling technique more appropriate. A proxy (approximate) population of 65,000 in the sample locations and a sample of 150 respondents were randomly selected. The returned questionnaires were collated, coded, entered as data entries and analyzed using SPSS version 16 and the findings were presented using descriptive and inferential statistics.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSIONS

From a total of 150 questionnaires administered to a cross-section of lecturers, students (Bias in architecture and environmental science), parents and other stakeholders in selected TVE institutions, a total of 143 questionnaires were returned after two weeks with consistent follow-ups by email, personal contact and phone calls. The response rate represents 95.3% of the entire questionnaire. The reliability test was conducted to test if the 24 items in the questionnaire instrument measured what it was intended to measure. The Cronbach Alpha based on standardized items indicated a magnitude of 0.892; an indication that the reliability condition is satisfactory. Table 1 reflected a balanced representation of genders, age groups, TVET stakeholders, TVET institutions as well as different education statuses of respondents.

The findings arising from the survey are hereby presented and discussed in Tables (1) below:

Table 1: Demographic Data of Respondents

Demographic Data	Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Sex	Male	83	58%
	Female	60	42%
Total		143	100%
Age	15-24 years	43	30.1%
	25-34 years	40	28.0%
	35-44 years	37	25.9%
	45-54 years	19	13.3%
	55 years and above	4	2.8%
Total		143	100%
Marital status	Single	68	47.6%
	Married	74	51.7%
	Widow	1	0.7%
Total		143	100%
Educational qualification	GCE O/Level	12	8.4%
	ND/NCE	15	10.5%
	HND	17	11.9%
	Bachelor	36	25.2%
	Masters and Doctoral	26	18.2%
	Others	37	25.9%
Total		143	100%
Which of the TVET institutions is you affiliated?			
	Kaduna Polytechnic, Kaduna,	37	25.9%
	Federal College of Education Zaria,	30	21.0%
	Nuhu Bamalli Polytechnic, Zaria	39	27.3%
	Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria	16	11.2%
	Others	21	14.7%
Total		143	100%
Status of the respondent in TVET Institution			
	Staff	53	37.1%
	Student	69	48.3%
	Parent	15	10.5%
	Contractor/Vendor/Friend of the institution	6	4.2%
Total		143	100.0%

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Table 2 shows that the majority of Nigerians think that TVET was designed for students who are weak in conventional education; some were of the view that TVET is an inferior education which is not suitable for brilliant students. The survey established that TVET has the potential of enhancing skills acquisition; promote self-employment, and technological progress as well as prepare students for the industry.

Table 2: Perception of TVET by the Nigerian Public

SN	Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Neither Agree nor Disagree (N) Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD)	SA	A	N	D	SD
1.	TVET is believed to be designed for students who cannot effectively cope with the rigour of the conventional education system.	16.8%	36.4%	11.2%	14.7%	21.0%
2.	The prevalent belief is that brilliant students should not take up TVET programmes.	14.7%	28.7%	16.1%	21.7%	18.9%
3.	TVET is perceived as an inferior education designed for students from poor families.	12.6%	28.0%	11.9%	23.1%	24.5%
4.	The essence of TVET as contained in the national policy on education is to enhance skills acquisition and promote self-employment.	50.3%	38.5%	7.7%	3.5%	-
5.	TVET unlike conventional education has the prospect of stimulating technological progress for national development.	46.9%	34.2%	13.3%	3.5%	2.1%
6.	TVET if well-positioned could become a mechanism for curbing the unemployment of graduates in the Nigerian competitive industry.	58.7%	28%	7.0%	4.9%	1.4%
7.	Formal or informal TVET helps prepare students adequately for the world of work and better performance in the industry.	41.3%	44.8%	12.6%	1.4%	-

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Table 3 indicated that the majority of the respondents agreed that quality assurance is observed in their respective TVET institutions despite several socio-economic challenges.

Table 3: *Quality Assurance Exercise in TVET Institutions*

SN	Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Neither Agree nor Disagree (N) Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD)	SA	A	N	D	SD
1.	Your affiliated TVET institution undergoes routine and periodic quality assurance exercises.	16.8%	50.3%	20.3%	10.5%	2.1%
2.	The importance of Quality assurance in your affiliated institution necessitated the establishment of a Quality Assurance Committee or Unit	21.7%	47.6%	17.5%	10.5%	-
3.	The essence of TVET Quality Assurance in most institutions is to strengthen the training outcomes and deliverables.	40.6%	45.5%	10.5%	1.4%	2.1%
4.	Quality assurance in your affiliated institution covers the competencies of instructors and instructional resources.	18.9%	49.7%	20.3%	7.0%	4.2%
5.	Quality assurance in your affiliated institution explores funding of TVET by the government.	16.8%	37.8%	32.2%	9.8%	3.5%
6.	Quality Assurance exercises are disliked by authorities and instructors in your affiliated institution because of socioeconomic challenges.	7.7%	32.9%	32.9%	16.1%	10.5%
7.	Philosophies of Quality Assurance are sacrificed by personal interests and institutional corruption.	10.5%	39.2%	32.9%	11.9%	5.6%
8.	Outcomes of Quality Assurance are at times positive despite infrastructural deficiencies.	23.1%	46.2%	17.5%	9.8%	3.5%

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Table 4 indicated that the majority of the respondents rated as fairly adequate the quality of TVET facilities like workshop rooms, books, learning environment, machines, computer rooms, TV/Audio-visual, instructors and contents of the curriculum.

Table 4: Quality of TVET Facilities in Your Institution

	TVET Items	Adequate	Fairly Adequate	Inadequate
1.	Workshop Rooms built for TVET	25.2%	60.1%	14.7%
2.	Books and reference materials on TVET available in the Library	20.3%	62.9%	16.8%
3.	Learning Environment for TVET	30.8%	57.3%	11.9%
4.	Machines, Equipment and Tools provided for TVET	27.3%	54.5%	18.2%
5.	Computer rooms set up for TVET	27.3%	44.8%	28.0%
6.	TV & Audiovisual used for TVET	16.1%	49.0%	35.0%
7.	TVET Instructors/Trainers	28.7%	50.3%	21.0%
8.	Contents of TVET curriculum to needs of the society	28.7%	54.5%	16.8%

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Table 5: Relevance of TVET Facilities in Your Institution

	TVET Items	Adequate	Fairly Adequate	Inadequate
1.	Workshop Rooms built for TVET	49.7%	43.3%	7.0%
2.	Books and reference materials on TVET are available in the Library	41.3%	53.1%	5.6%
3.	Learning Environment for TVET	50.3%	40.6%	9.1%
4.	Machines, Equipment and Tools provided for TVET	44.1%	47.6%	8.4%
5.	Computer rooms set up for TVET	42%	43.4%	14.7%
6.	TV & Audiovisual used for TVET	30.1%	44.8%	25.2%
7.	TVET Instructors/Trainers	39.9%	40.6%	19.6%
8.	Contents of TVET curriculum to needs of the society	42.0%	41.3%	16.8%

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Table 5 indicated that the rating of the relevance of the TVET facilities like workshop rooms, books, learning environment, machines, computer rooms, TV/Audiovisual, instructors and contents of the curriculum was mixed. Overall, a little above 40% of the respondents felt the TVET facilities are relevant, the same number of respondents noted that TVET facilities in place are relevant and the remaining 10% noted that TVET facilities

are irrelevant. Like the core finding in Table 4 earlier, there is an urgent need for the relevance of TVET facilities in Nigeria to be enhanced and upgraded to meet the needs of the industry and stakeholders.

Table 6: Challenges facing TVET.

SN	Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Neither Agree nor Disagree (N) Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD)	SA	A	N	D	SD
1.	Inadequate instructional resources affect the effectiveness of TVET programmes in your affiliated institution.	35.0%	49.7%	9.1%	2.1%	4.2%
2.	Poor conditions of service and motivation for instructors hinder the effectiveness of TVET in your institutions.	31.5%	51.0%	10.5%	2.8%	4.2%
3.	Irregular capacity-building and training for those handling TVET programmes affect training outcomes.	32.2%	50.3%	11.9%	1.4%	4.2%
4.	The inadequacy of experts and well-trained TVET instructors affects students' performances in vocational education.	37.1%	43.4%	11.2%	4.2%	4.2%
5.	Poor funding of TVET instructional resources hinders technological progress in Kaduna state, Nigeria.	41.3%	42.7%	8.4%	3.5%	4.2%
6.	Endemic corruption in the management of TVET programmes perpetuates unemployment and underdevelopment in Kaduna state, Nigeria.	36.4%	37.1%	18.9%	2.8%	4.9%

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Table 6 shows that between 60%-80% of the respondent identified inadequate instructional resources, the inadequacy of TVET experts/instructors, poor conditions of service for instructors, irregular capacity-building/training and endemic corruption as critical challenges affecting the quality of TVET in Kaduna state, Nigeria.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

This paper analyzes the impact of quality assurance on TVET in the field of architecture and environmental science in institutions in Kaduna State, Nigeria. It reveals that TVET was designed for students who are weak in conventional education and that the majority of the respondents agreed that quality assurance is observed in their respective TVET

institutions despite several socio-economic challenges. It also revealed that above 40% of the respondents felt that the TVET facilities are relevant.

5.2 Recommendations

Following the key findings in the tables above, the following recommendations are critical for developing an enduring quality assurance (QA) that would impact positively on TVET in Kaduna state, Nigeria.

- a) For TVET to stimulate employability and national development there is a need for proper sensitization and education of the general public including the policymakers on the real essence of TVET as it relates to architecture and environmental science disciplines. This measure, when properly carried out would fast-track attitudinal change and elicit positive commitment from parents, students, wards and all other stakeholders in Kaduna state.
- b) The Federal Government and stakeholders should provide adequate funding for TVET institutions to meet national aspirations. Adequate funding would boost standards and quality of manpower, instructional resources and infrastructural resources in vocational institutions in Kaduna state, Nigeria.
- c) Exchange programme between Industry and TVET institutions is inevitable for effective TVET outcomes that meet the industry's needs and the needs of individuals for self-employment and improved productivity in architecture and environmental science disciplines. Exchange arrangements often bridge the gaps between theory and practice as well as acquaint the trainers and trainees of TVET/VTE/IEI institutions with the present needs and expectations in the industry. This is otherwise called the Town-Gown relationship.
- d) TVET institutions should invest massively in routine and periodic capacity-building training programmes for teachers/lecturers/instructors in architecture and environmental science disciplines. This effort would keep trainers informed of best practices and methodological changes in the field of architecture and environmental science in Kaduna state.
- e) The Ministry of Education in collaboration with the supervisory agencies should embark on a sensitization campaign through the mass media to enrich public understanding and perception on the socio-economic benefits of TVET. This is

needed to correct the negative stereotyping of students on different TVET programmes in Kaduna state.

- f) To ensure effective curriculum implementation, there is a need for the supervisory agencies to ensure all TVET institutions implement uniform standards, training, evaluation and certification in federal, state and local government areas. At present there is variance in the certification patterns of formal and informal TVET institutions especially now that approval had been granted to VTEs and IEIs.
- g) The Federal Government of Nigeria should muster the political will to promote TVET as a springboard for the nation's technological progress, industrialization and National Development beyond the present rhetoric. The policy-makers in the Ministry of Education must go beyond rhetoric by genuinely according to special attention to TVET in architecture and environmental science disciplines in Kaduna state, Nigeria.

6. References

- Adebakin, M. A., and Raimi, L. (2012). National Security Challenges and Sustainable Economic Development: Evidence from Nigeria. *Journal of Studies in Social Sciences*, Vol. 1 (1), pp. 1-30.
- Amodu, T. (2011). Revamping Our National Economy through Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET). Available: <http://www.nigerianbestforum.com/blog/revamping-our-national-economy-through-technical-vocational-education-and-training-tvet/> (Accessed: 11 December 2015).
- Amuta, U. (2013). Nigeria spends N1.2trn annually on ICT goods imports. *Manufacturing Today* February 25 Edition. <http://www.manufacturingtodaynigeria.com/index.php/latest-news/150-news/6266-nigeria-spends-n12trn-annually-on-ict-goods-import> (Accessed: 22 August 2015).
- Badawi, A, A. (2013). TVET and entrepreneurship skills (Chapter 8). In revisiting global trends in TVET: Reflections on theory and practice. UNESCO-UNEVOC International Centre for Technical and Vocational Education and Training. Available: http://www.unevoc.unesco.org/fileadmin/up/2013_epub_revisiting_global_trends_in_tvete_bok.pdf (Accessed: 24 September 2015).
- Ball, S.J. (1994). Researching inside the state: Issues in the interpretation of elite interviews. In Halpin, D. and Troyna, B. (eds.) *Researching Education Policy: Ethical and methodological issues*. London, Falmer Press.
- Becker. G. (2009). *Human Capital: A Theoretical and Empirical Analysis with Special Reference to Education*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press.
- Bowles, S., and Gintis, H. (1976). *Schooling in Capitalist America*, London: Routledge and Kegan Paul.
- Broudy, H. S. (1981). *Toward a Theory of Vocational Education*. Occasional Paper No. 73. Available: <http://breakthroughs.education.illinois.edu/publications/toward-theory-vocational-education-occasional-paper-no-73> (Accessed: 19 September 2015).
- Borden, V., & Bottrill, K. (1994). Performance Indicators; Histories, Definitions and Methods. *New Directions for Institutional Research*, 82, pp. 5-21.
- Cave, M., Hanney, S., Henkel, M., and Kogan, M. (1997). *The Use of Performance Indicators in Higher Education: The Challenge of the Quality Movement* (3rd Ed.). London: Jessica. Kingsley.
- Chalmers, D. (2008). Teaching and Learning Quality Indicators in Australian Universities, Conference proceedings of Institutional Management in Higher Education (IMHE), Paris France, September 8-12.

- Cheng, Y. C. (2001). Paradigm Shifts in Quality Improvement in Education: Three Waves for the Future, Speech Presented at The International Forum on Quality Education for the Twenty-first Century, Beijing, China, 12-15 June.
- Ehintero, S. (2004). Accountability and quality assurance in Nigerian education. Paper presented at the international conference of the Institute of Education, Olabisi Onabanjo University, Ago-Iwoye. (Jan 12th -15th).
- Eze, T. I., and Okorafor, O. A. (2012). Trends in technical, vocational education and training for improving the Nigerian workforce. *Ebonyi Vocational and Technology Education Journal*, Vol.1(1), pp.107-115.
- Fadokun, J. B. (2005). Educational assessment and quality assurance implication for principal instructional leadership roles. Paper presented at the 31st Annual Conference of International Association for Educational Assessment 4-9 September, Abuja.
- Filloux, J. (1993). Emile Durkheim (1858-1917). *PROSPECTS*, UNESCO: International Bureau of Education, Vol. 23(1/2), pp. 303–320.
- Gabadeen, W. O., and Raimi, L. (2012). Management of Entrepreneurship Education in Nigerian Higher Institutions: Issues, Challenges and Way Forward. *Abuja International Journal of Education and Management Sciences (ABIJEMS)*, 2, pp. 1-26.
- National Board for Technical Education (2011). List of Approved VEIs/IEIs in Nigeria by NBTE. Available: http://www.nbte.gov.ng/inst_07.html (Accessed: 18 November 2015).
- Adebakin, M. A. (2012). National Security Challenges and Sustainable Economic Development: Evidence from Nigeria. In *Journal of Studies in Social Sciences* (Vol. 1).
- Adegbesan, S. O. (2011). Establishing quality assurance in the Nigerian education system: Implication for educational managers. *Educational Research and Reviews*, 6(2), 147–151. <http://www.academicjournals.org/ERR>

Author(s)

1

Fatima Baba Ciroma

She is currently a lecturer, Principal Lecturer (PL) at Kaduna Polytechnic in Nigeria. She holds a master's degree in architecture and a B. Tech in Architecture from Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi. Her lecturing career began in 2010 at the Department of Architecture at Kaduna Polytechnic, where she currently teaches Architecture related courses and holds other responsibilities within the Department. Fatima is currently pursuing a Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Architecture at Ahmadu Bello University Zaria. Fatima has actively participated in various International and National Conferences and Workshops. She is a member of several professional organizations, including the Nigerian Institute of Architects (ANIA), provisional membership with the Architects Registration Council of Nigeria (ARCON), Association of Architectural Educators of Nigeria (AARCHES), Women in Technical Education and Development (WITED), Nigerian Environmental Society (NES), Green Building Council of Nigeria (GBCN), and Teachers Registration Council (TRCN), among others. In addition to her teaching responsibilities, Fatima serves as the admissions and Registration officer of the Department of Architecture at Kaduna Polytechnic. She is also, a member of the Management Committee on Junior Staff Appointments and Promotions (MCJSA&PC) and the College of Environmental Studies conference committee (CES conference), among other roles. Her research interests primarily revolve around Anti-Terrorism Crime Prevention and Security Design.

2

Aisha Wali Aminu-Umar

She is currently a Lecturer at Kaduna Polytechnic, has been teaching Architecture related courses and holds other responsibilities within the Department amongst others. Master's degree (MSc Arch) holder from Architecture Department, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria. She holds membership with the Association of Architectural Educators in Nigeria (AARCHES), Nigerian Institute of Architects (NIA), Teachers Registration Council (TRCN), Provisional Membership with the Architects Registration Council of

Nigeria (ARCON), and Nigerian Environmental Society (NES).

3

Ndandok, Christy Thyeno

She is an experienced Architect for over a decade specializing in residential and Institutional (Educational) buildings. Her special interests are sustainable design solutions and construction. She also lectures at the Department of Architecture Kaduna Polytechnic as a

principal lecturer.